

Single-cell mRNA expression of PBMCs reveal dynamic immunomodulatory features of metastatic breast cancer

Mangiola S¹, Pal B², et al.

¹The Walter and Eliza Hall Institute of Medical Research, Parkville, Victoria 3052, Australia.

²Olivia Newton-John Cancer Research Institute, Heidelberg Vic 3084 Australia.

Abstract

Several single-cell studies have reported transcriptomic, genomic and epigenomic dysregulation in breast cancer. However, the peripheral immune landscape of breast cancer remains poorly understood. We report an integrated analysis of the single-cell transcriptomes of more than 65,000 peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) of stable oligometastatic and progressive metastatic breast cancer patients. Deconvolution of PBMCs revealed major myeloid and lymphoid immune cells, including rare T cell lineages of MAIT and Gamma delta T cells, thus revealing previously unreported immune subsets in metastatic breast cancer. Regardless of the extent of the metastatic burden, the cancer patients profile indicates global enrichment of proinflammatory NKG7 high monocytes, M1 macrophages, migratory myeloid, T memory stem cells (T_{SCM}), CD4 T effector memory (T_{EM}) and CD4 T central memory (T_{CM}) cells. Interrogation with healthy donor's PBMCs single-cell transcriptome shows marked depletion of memory B cells (B_{MEM}), transitional CD8, CD4 central memory (T_{CM}) and MAIT cells in the circulating immune landscape of metastatic breast cancer patients. This suggests that peripheral immune cells can provide a surrogate marker for undiagnosed metastasis.

Comparative analysis of stable versus progressive metastatic disease states shows distinct compositional and gene expression changes in PBMCs. The antigen inexperienced CD4 naïve and cytotoxic MAIT cells are relatively depleted in progressive metastatic disease. While the pro-inflammatory classical monocytes and CD4 T effector memory (T_{EM}) cell levels are elevated in stable metastasis, they diminish in the progressive metastatic state. The receptor-ligand relationship analysis between the two metastatic cohorts revealed unique cell-cell contact, ECM-receptor interactions, and cytokine profile, thus identifying potential new therapeutic targets for metastatic disease. Overall, our study provides a novel resource on the peripheral immune system operating in metastatic breast cancer.

Figure 1. Integrated single-cell transcriptome profile of metastatic breast cancer patient's PBMCs. **A.** Integrated UMAP plot of scRNAseq profile from ten metastatic breast cancer patients. Each dot represents a single cell and patient marked by a unique colour. **B.** Integrated UMAP plot depicting four major immune cell types (B cell, T cell + NK cells, monocyte-derived, and plasmacytoid dendritic cells). **C.** UMAP plot showing relative transcriptional abundance of four major cell types based on cardinal lineage markers. **D.** Summary of the scaled relative transcript abundance of the marker genes for the four major cell types. **E.** UMAP plot of the lymphocytes reanalysed in isolation, coloured by immune cell type. **F.** UMAP plot coloured by relative transcriptional abundance of known marker genes for lymphocytes. **G.** Summary of the scaled relative transcript abundance of the marker genes for the lymphocytes. **H.** UMAP plot of the myeloid cells reanalysed in isolation, coloured by cell type. **I.** UMAP plot coloured by relative transcriptional abundance of marker genes for the myeloid. **J.** Summary of the scaled relative transcript abundance of the marker genes for the myeloid types.

Figure 2. Rare MAIT and gamma-delta T cells are present in the blood of metastatic breast cancer patients. **A.** Heat map showing top differentially expressed known marker genes of MAIT cells compared to other lymphocytes. The heatmap is coloured by the row-scaled relative abundance of marker-gene transcripts. **B.** UMAP plot of the reclustered MAIT cells, coloured by the relative transcript abundance of the six marker genes. **C.** Top differentially expressed known marker genes of gamma-delta T cells compared to other lymphocytes. The heatmap is coloured by the row-scaled relative abundance of marker-gene transcripts. **D.** UMAP plot of the gamma-delta T cells reanalysed in isolation, coloured by cell cluster. **E.** Heat map showing expression profile of known marker genes of gamma-delta T cell clusters reanalysed in **panel D**. The heatmap is coloured by the row-scaled relative abundance of marker-gene transcripts. **F.** UMAP plot of the gamma-delta T cells, coloured by the relative transcript abundance of the top 12 marker genes.

Figure 3. Comparative analysis with healthy PBMCs reveal differential composition and transcriptome of PBMCs in metastatic breast cancer patients. **A.** Integrated UMAP plot of ten healthy (blue) and ten metastatic (yellow) single-cell transcriptome profiles. Labels indicate cell types that are differentially abundant between the two conditions. **B.** PCA plot of the 20 pseudo-bulk transcriptomes, coloured by condition. **C.** Differential composition between Cancer and healthy. Dots are coloured by cell type (see Figure 1E and 1H). On the left-hand side are cell types enriched in healthy individuals, while on the right-hand side for cancer patients. The error bars represent the 95% credible interval for the estimates. The bold dot borders represent the significantly enriched cell types, where the 95% credible interval of the effect is bigger than 0.2 (or smaller than -0.2). **D.** Proportion distributions of the top enriched cell types coloured by condition. The red dots represent outlier observations detected by scomp (10.18129/B9.bioc.scomp). **E.** Top results for the gene-wise differential transcript abundance analysis. Boxplots represent the distribution for the scaled transcript

abundance of the cell-type/sample-specific pseudo-bulk data. The colour represents the conditions. The top five genes are displayed for the top transcriptionally distinct cell type. **F.** Spatial transcriptomic-derived cell type abundance for HER2+ primary breast cancer, liver metastases from ER+ (LumA subtype) breast cancer and benign breast tissue. The pixels are coloured by the proportion of epithelial, endothelial, myeloid and lymphoid cells (from right to left).

Figure 4. Metastatic breast cancer stage defines heterogeneity and molecular characteristics of PBMCs. **A.** Integrated UMAP plot of scRNAseq profile from ten metastatic breast cancer patients. Single cells are marked by metastatic stage: Green - Oligometastatic (OMBC) and orange - metastatic breast cancer (MBC). **B.** PCA plot of the 10 pseudo-bulk transcriptomes, coloured by condition. **C.** Differential composition between

Cancer and healthy. Dots are coloured by cell type (see Figure 1E and 1H). On the left-hand side are cell types enriched in healthy individuals, while on the right-hand side for cancer patients. The error bars represent the 95% credible interval for the estimates. The bold dot borders represent the significantly enriched cell types, where the 95% credible interval of the effect is bigger than 0.2 (or smaller than -0.2). **D.** Scaled transcription abundance of cell-type-specific pseudo-bulk samples, for the differentially abundant gene-transcripts. The top transcriptionally distinct cell types between conditions are included. The samples are coloured accordingly with their condition. The genes are coloured accordingly with their main class. **E.** Top results for the gene-wise differential transcript abundance analysis. Boxplots represent the distribution for the scaled transcript abundance of the cell-type/sample-specific pseudo-bulk data. The colour represents the conditions. The top two genes are displayed for the top transcriptionally distinct cell type. **F.** Spatial transcriptomic-derived cell type abundance for HER2+ and LumA liver metastases. The pixels are coloured by the proportion of cell types. **G.** Compositional average across samples within data source for the single-cell and spatial transcriptomics data. The stacked barplot is coloured by cell types (see Figure 1E and 1H).

Figure 5. Stable oligometastatic versus progressive metastatic disease show differential immune crosstalk profiles. **A.** Count of highly transcribed ligand-receptor pairs for each sample across conditions. The communication axes were grouped by cell-cell interaction, extracellular matrix (ECM) receptors, and long-distance secreted signalling. Colours represent conditions. The red diamond indicated the average count across samples. **B.** Enrichment scored for cell-type/communication axes. Each communication axis can underlie

several ligands and receptors. The colours represent the enrichment direction (blue for stable and red for progressive disease). Communication axes are grouped by type. Bar plots represent the enrichment score average for cell types (columns) or communication axes (rows). **C.** Enrichment of communication among cell types for the most differentially enriched (in either one direction) communication axes. The colours represent the enrichment direction (blue for stable and red for progressive disease). The genes included in each communication axis are below the names of the communication axes. The arrows represent the direction of the communication (ligand outgoing, receptor incoming). Some communication is bi-directional. **D.** Transcript abundance for the ALCAM/CD6 ligand/receptor pair, for the cell types that show enrichment (dendritic cells with ligand and lymphocytes with the receptor). Colours represent conditions. **E.** UMAP plot of cells coloured by transcription of either ALCAM or CD6. **F.** Transcript abundance for the CLEC/KLRB1 ligand/receptor pair, for the cell types that show enrichment. Colours represent conditions. **G:** UMAP plot of cells coloured by transcription of either CLEC or KLRB1.